

Adaptive Strategies amidst an Emerging Educational Trend: What Teachers Should Know?

Samson M. Lausa¹, Lover Joy N. Embao²

¹*Northern Negros State College of Science and Technology, Sagay City, Negros Occidental, Philippines*

²*Dreamland School of Murcia, Inc*

Corresponding email: smlausa@nonescost.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

This study examined the flexible learning strategies of pupils of one private elementary school in Negros Occidental, Philippines enrolled in the school year 2020-2021. This quantitative study used a descriptive method with 88 pupils who responded to the validated and reliability-tested survey questionnaire. The frequency and percentage distribution, mean, t-test, ANOVA, and Pearson R Product Moment of Correlation Coefficient were used to interpret the results of the study. The findings indicated that participants' sexual profile, grade level, and sample size were evenly distributed. The use of; planning strategy, doing strategy, reflection strategy, emotional response strategy, and helpline strategy as adaptive learning strategies in flexible learning modality is to a great extent. Moreover, findings showed that no significant difference exists in the utilization of these adaptive strategies except in the aspect of age, educational background, and occupation of the father which showed significant results. Likewise, a significant relationship was revealed between the adaptive learning strategies and the academic achievement of participants as a whole and when grouped as to learning strategy.

ARTICLE INFO

Received : Jan. 31, 2023

Revised : Apr. 12, 2023

Accepted : June 30, 2023

KEYWORDS

Adaptive learning strategies, Emerging educational trend, Flexible learning, Learning support strategy, Learning strategy plan

Suggested Citation (APA Style 7th Edition):

Lausa, S.M. & Embao, L.J.N. (2023). Adaptive Strategies amidst an Emerging Educational Trend: What Teachers Should Know? *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 3(2), 12-28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8139666>

INTRODUCTION

Learning is one of the individuals' life processes that serves as a function or mechanism that drives personal and academic development. During COVID-19 pandemic as considered by many as educational crisis, the education system underwent rapid change. This condition has affected the education systems not only in the Philippines, but worldwide and compelled educators to ensure continuity of education. Distance learning solutions were created as a result of swift responses from governments and partners all around the world who promote education continuity, including the Global Education Coalition. which has highlighted the imperative of leaving no one behind (UNESCO, G.D., 2020).

According to the evaluation of several researchers, it is uncertain that the traditional face-to-face teaching-learning process will return. The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Department of Education (DepEd) has even stated that a "traditional" face-to-face class is no longer effective in the present time. Physical distancing measures are prevalent at this time; changes in teaching-learning like instructional delivery, assessments, learning environment, and learning mode will have an impact on how learners will learn. These events highlight the need for academic institutions to prioritize organization (Riley, 2020). As a result, within the emerging educational trend, learners' adaptive strategies have become an important factor in personal and academic progress as it will drive teachers to innovate their teaching strategies and initiatives to address the changing needs of learners as they adapt to the change of the education landscape.

Teaching is now taking place in the digital realm, which has drastically altered education. It has been told that the online mode of learning is easily obtainable and can even get through rural and remote areas. It is relatively counted as an inexpensive mode of learning in terms of transportation, convenience, and the overall amount of school-based learning. Flexibility is a further fascinating facet of online learning; a student can designate their time to complete their available learning resources. This mode of learning can build up the learning capabilities of the learners. Learners can learn anytime and anywhere, hence acquiring new skills in the system paving the way for learners' adaptive strategies heading to life-long learning (Dhawan, 2020).

Parents' desire for their children to excel academically even during pandemic or crisis puts great pressure on students, teachers, and in general, the education system. It appears that the whole education system revolves around student learning strategy plans in this new standard. Thus, academic leaders, planners, and psychologists have spent and will continue to spend ample time and effort on finding various strategies to loosen the complexities of making learners learn, identify effective learning habits, and other personality variables such as self-esteem, anxiety, and motivation (Means, 2020). Learning habits, which reflect an individual's personality as shaped by their learning experiences, are a critical element in students' pursuit of academic success.

The researchers were impressed by this fact, which leads for this study to emerge with a focus on the investigation of adaptive learning strategies of the pupils of one private elementary school in Negros Occidental in SY 2020-2021.

Research Problem

This study aimed to determine the adaptive learning strategies of the pupils of one private elementary school in Negros Occidental enrolled in the School Year 2020-2021. Specifically, it sought to determine the extent of utilization of the following adaptive learning strategies; planning, doing, reflection, emotional response, and helpline strategy. These strategies were found to be among the strategies that measures adaptability of learners as cited by previous studies deemed applicable to the present study. A significant difference in the extent of utilization of these learning strategies based on the variables; age, sex, grade level, educational attainment and occupation of the parents, size of family, and number of siblings are also measured. Likewise, a relationship between adaptive learning strategies

and the participants' academic achievement as a whole and when grouped as to strategy is also established. The academic achievement used for this study is the final grade of pupil-participants categorized as to level based on the Department of Education grading system.

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were drawn in relation to the aforementioned issues: There is no significant difference in the extent of utilization of the adaptive learning strategies when pupils are grouped according to the profile. There is no significant correlation between the extent of utilization of the adaptive learning strategies and pupils' academic achievement when grouped as to strategy and as a whole,

Methodology

Research Design

To achieve the objectives outlined in the study, the descriptive method in quantitative design was used utilizing a survey questionnaire for investigating the relationship among the variables and learning strategies toward emerging educational trends. Participants in this study were the 88 primary pupils of one private elementary school. Data validation was done through interviews with the parents of the participants to draw their insights and observations as to how their children strategized learning processes or activities through their learning strategy plan to cope with the new mode of instructional delivery. The researchers used the total enumeration considering that the number of pupil-participants is manageable.

There were three bases for the adaptive learning strategies questionnaire, one of which is the Learning Strategies Questionnaire by the Centre for the Study of Learning and Performance which consisted of 45 statements. Since some of the statements were not clear to the students, the researchers underwent modifications keeping 25 items. Another basis was the Learning Strategic Tool: TOJET Questionnaire Confirmation: Turkish Online Journal of Technology - August 2015, Special Edition of INTE 2015 which consisted of 27 questions that were modified to which common concepts were lumped and integrated into the instrument. The third basis was the Validation of Self-Regulated Online Learning Questionnaire (October 25, 2016) which consisted of 36 questions, but only four under the helpline strategy were integrated into the final instrument. The three were selected as based for the final instrument as it exhibits a comprehensive evaluation of the adaptive learning strategies that the current study is pursuing. Modifications such as exclusions, revisions, and translations of some of the items are done to make it more appropriate in the Philippine Education System of the DepEd and of the level of the pupil-participants.

To answer the problems postulated in this study the final survey questionnaire was made of three parts, Part I is the general information of the participants including their names and age. Part II of the instrument is the profile of the participants such as; sex, grade level, educational attainment and occupation of their parents, and the number and educational attainment of sibling/s. Part III measures the extent of utilization of participants of the adaptive learning strategies using flexible learning delivery. This part consists of five adaptive learning strategies namely the planning strategy, the doing strategy, the reflection strategy, the emotional-response strategy, and the helpline strategy. Each parameter has seven indicators except for the helpline strategy, which only contains six indicators. In each indicator, five alternative responses for the participants to choose from were provided according to their self-assessment on how they adapt the learning strategy. Likewise, each indicator is also translated into "Filipino" to ensure that the participants understand the statements and gave the objective rating.

The questionnaire's validity and reliability were established at 0.91 and 0.920 using the item-content validity index (I-CVI) by Waltz and Bausell and Cronbach Alpha, respectively. The researchers upon approval of the school administrator personally administer the conduct of the study. Participants and their parents were contacted personally

and were given an orientation on the purpose of the study, and the data collection process and were made to understand that their participation is voluntary, hence, participating or withdrawing from the study while it is in progress will not harm them and the study.

Respondents and the parent/guardian were given time to read the information sheet and decide whether or not they wanted to participate in the study. The purpose of the study was explained to them and they were informed that they can withdraw from participating the study at any point in time if they believed that the study poses any harm or danger. The researchers assured the respondents that the anonymity and confidentiality of their responses were maintained by disclosing their names and identities in data collection, analysis, and reporting of research findings and the publication and dissemination of results at conferences or research fields. With the guidance of the parent/guardian, all respondents of the study were asked to sign an informed consent form before the administration of the questionnaire, indicating their permission to be part of the study.

Data analysis used includes; frequency and percentage distribution for the profile, mean and standard deviation for the extent of utilization of the adaptive learning strategies, t-test and ANOVA for the test of difference on the extent of utilization, and the Pearson R Product Moment of Correlation Coefficient was used in determining relationship between utilization of adaptive learning strategies and the pupils' academic achievement.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Profile of Respondents

Profile Variables	f	%
<i>Age</i>		
8-10 years old	54	61.4
11-13 years old	34	38.6
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	45	51.1
Female	43	48.9
<i>Grade Level</i>		
grade 3	24	27.3
grade 4	18	20.5
grade 5	25	28.4
grade 6	21	23.9
<i>Education of Mother</i>		
high school	9	10.2
college level	19	21.6
college graduate	56	63.6
postgraduate	4	4.5
<i>Education of Father</i>		
high school	9	10.2
college level	28	31.8
college graduate	48	54.5
postgraduate	3	3.4
<i>Occupation of Mother</i>		
housewife	30	34.1
Laborer	57	64.8
caste occupation	1	1.1
<i>Occupation of Father</i>		

unemployed	55	62.5
laborer	33	37.5
Total	88	100.0
<i>Size of Family</i>		
1-4 members	31	35.0
above 4 members	57	65.0
<i>Number of Siblings</i>		
no sibling	29	33.0
with 1-3 siblings	8	9.1
with the above 3 siblings	51	58.0

There were around 88 pupils from Grade 3 to Grade 6 and all of them participated in the study conducted. Of the total sample group, 61.4% of pupils have ages ranging from 8-to 10 years old, and 38.6% for 11-13 years old. Among the respondents, 51.1% were boys and 49.9% were girls. Per grade level, 27.3% were from Grade 3, 20.5% from Grade 4, 28.4% from Grade 5, and 23.9% from Grade 6.

It also revealed that only 35% of the sample size belong to small size families and 65% were from medium to large-sized families. In terms of the number of siblings, 33% of the respondents have no siblings, while 9.1% have one-three siblings and 58% have three or more siblings.

Of the respondents' parents, both the father and mother of the respondents indicated 10.2% for high school level; 21.6% of mothers and 31.8% of fathers were in college-level. 63.6% of respondents' mothers and 54.5% of fathers were college graduates, and 4.5% of the respondents' mothers and 3.4 percent of the fathers had reached postgraduate. It was observed that there were no illiterate parents among the respondents.

Further, results revealed that 34.1% of mothers are housewives and 62.5% of the respondents' fathers are unemployed; 64.8% of mothers and 37.5% of fathers are laborers, and 1.1% of the respondents' mothers, and none of the respondents' fathers are having caste occupation. This indicates that, on average, 48.3% of the respondents' parents have zero to low income.

Table 2 Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Planning Strategies

Planning Strategies	M	SD.	VI
1. I start by setting goals for myself. (<i>Nagsisimula ako sa pagtatakda ng layunin para sa aking sarili.</i>)	3.5909	1.04646	Great Extent
2. I plan the steps to complete my task. (<i>Nagpaplano ako ng mga hakbang upang makumpleto ang mga gawain.</i>)	3.6705	1.15193	Great Extent
3. I set my goals to help me manage my studying time. (<i>Itinatakda ko ang aking mga layunin upang mapamahalaan ang aking pag-aaral.</i>)	3.7159	1.02776	Great Extent
4. I try to consider the significance and the usefulness of what I am going to study. (<i>Sinisikap kong maisaalang-alang ang kabuluhan at kapakinabangan ng aking pag-aaralan.</i>)	3.7841	1.09805	Great Extent
5. I scan my lesson and start with the easiest or most attractive activity so that it is possible to have an interest in studying. (<i>Kinikilatis ko ang aking mga aralin mula sa pinakamadali o kaakit-akit na gawain upang magkaroon ng interes sa pag-aaral.</i>)	3.9659	1.16903	Great Extent
6. I use relaxation techniques before I start studying. (<i>Pinapahinga ko muna ang aking sarili bago mag-aral.</i>)	3.6705	1.09041	Great Extent

7. I start by relating the topics I am going to study with my interests. (<i>Nagsisimula ako sa pag-uugnay sa paksang pag-aralan na aking interes.</i>)	3.6705	1.06912	Great Extent
Mean	3.7240	.77183	Great Extent

Table 2 shows the great extent of the utilization of adaptive learning in planning strategies in seven indicators. The results implied that the pupils were undertaking planning activities before the learning process, as affirmed by the parents during the interview that somehow their children are doing some preparatory tasks before studying their lessons.

Table 2.1 Differences in the Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Planning Strategies when grouped According to Selected Variables

Profile Variables	M	SD	Df	F	P	VI
<i>Age</i>						
8-10 years old	3.7963	.72557	1	1.229	.271	Not Significant
11-13 years old	3.6092	.83840				
<i>Sex</i>						
male	3.5175	.79847	1	7.055	.009	Significant
female	3.9402	.68741				
<i>Grade Level</i>						
grade 3	3.8155	.80314	3	.944		Not Significant
grade 4	3.7143	.68249		.423		
grade 5	3.8400	.76523				
grade 6	3.4898	.81638				
<i>Education of Father</i>						
high school	3.8155	.80314	3	4.203	.008	Significant
college level	3.7143	.68249				
college graduate	3.8400	.76523				
postgraduate	3.4898	.81638				
<i>Education of Mother</i>						
high school	3.6190	.81754	3	.080	.971	Not Significant
college level	3.7444	.68937				
college graduate	3.7398	.79754				
postgraduate	3.6429	.96539				
<i>Occupation of Father</i>						
Unemployed	3.6104	.73384	1	3.262	.074	Not Significant
Laborer	3.9134	.80728				
<i>Occupation of Mother</i>						
Housewife	3.5619	.80545	2	1.053	.353	Not Significant
Laborer	3.8120	.75311				
caste occupation	3.5714	.				
<i>Size of Family</i>						
1-4 members	3.6558	.78204	1	.227	.635	Not Significant
above 4 members	3.7468	.77309				
<i>Number of Siblings</i>						
no sibling	3.6010	.77061	2	.565	.570	Not Significant
with 1-3 siblings	3.7321	.95812				
with above 3 siblings	3.7927	.74959				

The data shows a significant difference between the two sexes in terms of adaptive learning utilizing planning strategies. It was also observed that the father's educational background has a significant influence on children's utilization of adaptive learning in planning strategies.

It implies, therefore, that females may have better learning strategies than males and that lack of time may also be a major reason why parents do not include their children's education, nevertheless, the child's support system gives ample time to direct the child's learning, the drive to plan to learn increases.

A study on the influences of gender differences in English learning conducted in China states that the learning strategy of females is more conscious than that of males (Qian, 2017). Likewise, the “No Child Left Behind Act” (NCLB) emphasizes that the involvement of the parents in students’ learning plays an essential role in the student’s success. In countless studies and reports, the important role of parental involvement in a child's education has been explored. The research overwhelmingly supports its numerous conclusions and one of which is that "time constraints are a major obstacle to parental involvement (Chen, 2020)."

Table 3 Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Doing Strategies

Doing Strategies	Mean	SD	VI
1. I remind myself of my goals as I am working.(<i>Pinaalalahanan ko ang sarili ng aking mga hangarin habang nagtatrabaho.</i>)	3.5341	1.16411	Great Extent
2. I give all my attention to the task I am doing.(<i>Binibigyan ko ng lubusang atensiyon ang aking mga ginagawa.</i>)	3.9091	1.08951	Great Extent
3. I turn the task into smaller, easier steps. (<i>Ginagawa ko ang mga gawain sa mas maliit o mas madaling hakbang.</i>)	3.7500	.97379	Great Extent
4. I seriously concentrate on studying. (<i>Seryoso sakong nakatuon sa pag-aaral.</i>)	3.8523	.92897	Great Extent
5. I retain my interest in what I am studying that I become unaware of time.(<i>Pinanatili ko ang interes sa aking pinag-aralan na hindi ko na napapansin ang oras.</i>)	3.3636	1.10570	Moderate
6. I remind myself to manage to learn what I am studying.(<i>Pinaalalahanan ko ang aking sarili na matutong matutunan ang aking pinag-aralan.</i>)	3.9091	1.07891	Great Extent
7. I create ideas or visualize my lessons to keep me motivated in my studies.(<i>Lumilikha ako ng ideya o pangitain sa mga aaralin upang patuloy na maganyak sa aking pinag-aralan.</i>)	3.7045	.93660	Great Extent
	Mean 3.7175	.75964	Great Extent

The data shows the extent of utilization of adaptive learning in doing strategies which indicates great extent in all aspects except for indicator five which shows a moderate result.

Table 3.1 Differences in the Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Doing Strategies when grouped According to Selected Variables

Profile Variables	Mean	SD	Df	F	P	VI
<i>Age</i>						
8-10 years old	3.7328	.76557	1	.056	.814	Not Significant
11-13 years old	3.6933	.76093				
<i>Sex</i>						
Male	3.5111	.80553	1	7.292	.008	Significant
Female	3.9336	.64970				
<i>Grade Level</i>						

grade 3	3.7560	.82063	3	1.348	.264	Not Significant
grade 4	3.5714	.78093				
grade 5	3.9371	.69140				
grade 6	3.5374	.72690				
<i>Education of Father</i>						
high school	3.0159	.70147	3	3.777	.014	Significant
college level	3.8316	.57545				
college graduate	3.7440	.80756				
postgraduate	4.3333	.59476				
<i>Education of Mother</i>						
high school	3.5556	.82203	3	.175	.913	Not Significant
college level	3.6917	.71470				
college graduate	3.7500	.78353				
postgraduate	3.7500	.71309				
<i>Occupation of Father</i>						
unemployed	3.6078	.77285	1	3.136	.080	Not Significant
laborer	3.9004	.71114				
<i>Occupation of Mother</i>						
housewife	3.5667	.81461	2	.899	.411	Not Significant
laborer	3.7945	.73094				
caste occupation	3.8571	.00000				
<i>Size of Family</i>						
1-4 members	3.7403	.77200	1	.026	.872	Not Significant
above 4 members	3.7100	.76130				
<i>Number of Siblings</i>						
no sibling	3.5961	.78531	2	.579	.563	Not Significant
with 1-3 siblings	3.7143	.96287				
with above 3 siblings	3.7871	.71792				

The result revealed that there is a significant difference between males and females, and the father's educational background. This suggests that females may have better utilization of doing strategy compared to males. It also showed that even though the educational background of a father occurred between a high school that obtained the lowest mean, a father's presence, and support allows the learner to have self-confidence and better utilization of doing strategy.

Sociologist Paul Amato studied the relationships between parent and child in Pennsylvania and explains that children do better when fathers are busy with their children. "For a child's growth, research reveals, that fathers are critical (Krisch, 2020)". Another study by the OECD acknowledges that the top of the class for centuries were boys, but these days, girls are achieving higher academic performance and do better than boys. This is because girls read more than boys, and they spend more time on homework than boys, who spend an average of 17% of their free time in the virtual world playing collaborative online games than girls everyday (Wilson, 2015).

Table 4 Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Reflection Strategies

Reflection Strategies	Mean	SD	VI
1. I check my work to see if I have done it well once I am finished. (<i>Sinisiguro ko na maayos kong nagawa ang aking mga gawain.</i>)	3.8068	1.14328	Great Extent
2. I do it well because I exerted much effort. (<i>Nagawa ko nang maayos ang aking gawain dahil pinaghirapan ko ito.</i>)	3.6705	1.01394	Great Extent

3. I do it well because my parent/s or sibling explains things clearly. (Nagawa ko nang maayos dahil ipinaliwanag ng mabuti ng aking magulang o kapatid ang mga bagay-bagay.)	4.1705	1.01960	Great Extent
4. I feel happy about the outcome of the performance. (Masaya ako sa aking ginawa.)	3.7614	1.16456	Great Extent
5. I value what I have learned. (Pinapahalagahan ko ang aking natutuhan.)	4.0114	1.06668	Great Extent
6. I analyze the causes of my declining will to study. (Sinusuri ko ang mga dahilan ng pagbaba nang hangarin ko sa pagkatuto o pag-aaral.)	3.3182	1.25529	Moderate
7. I consider pleasant study situations to have more interest in my studies. (Isinasaalang-alang ko ang mga kaaya-ayang sitwasyon sa pagkatuto.)	3.9886	1.06668	Great Extent
Mean	3.8182	.74961	Great Extent

“Analysing the causes of declining will to study” in indicator number six of table 4 results in moderate extent. All remaining indicators resulted to great extent in students’ adaptive learning in reflection strategy. This reflects that students and parents can adapt quickly and happily to this kind of learning strategy despite the new mode of learning.

Table 4.1 Differences in the Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Reflection Strategies when grouped According to Selected Variables

Profile Variables	Mean	SD	Df	F	P	VI
<i>Age</i>						
8-10 years old	3.8042	.74531	1	.048	.827	Not Significant
11-13 years old	3.8403	.76711				
<i>Sex</i>						
Male	3.6508	.77205	1	4.792	.031	Significant
Female	3.9934	.69144				
<i>Grade Level</i>						
grade 3	3.8036	.73427	3	1.834	.147	Not Significant
grade 4	3.6111	.77909				
grade 5	4.0914	.71295				
grade 6	3.6871	.74041				
<i>Education of Father</i>						
high school	3.1746	.67679	3	4.633	.005	Significant
college level	4.0867	.59773				
college graduate	3.7470	.77926				
postgraduate	4.3810	.21822				
<i>Education of Mother</i>						
high school	3.4762	.65465	3	.881	.455	Not Significant
college level	3.9699	.76425				
college graduate	3.8214	.75948				
postgraduate	3.8214	.75930				
<i>Occupation of Father</i>						
unemployed	3.7558	.74316	1	1.014	.317	Not Significant
laborer	3.9221	.76021				
<i>Occupation of Mother</i>						
housewife	3.7333	.72138	2	.576	.564	Not Significant
laborer	3.8521	.76929				
caste occupation	4.4286	.				
<i>Size of Family</i>						
1-4 members	3.8896	.73630	1	.264	.609	Not Significant
above 4 members	3.7944	.75806				

<i>Number of Siblings</i>						
no sibling	3.6700	.78627	2	.846	.433	Not Significant
with 1-3 siblings	3.9107	.92877				
with above 3 siblings	3.8880	.70120				

Table 4.1 shows a significant result on the respondents' sex and the educational attainment of the respondent's fathers. This shows that there are different adjustment levels between males and females, guided by their father as one of their support systems in their journey toward flexible online learning. The remaining indicators have no significant influence on this variable.

There is no question that parenting styles impact a child's well-being in the future. It is often motherhood that dominates the parenting, according to studies, rather than the father. However, when children have a close relationship with their fathers, they are more likely to avoid risky behaviors and are less likely to drop out from school (Krisch, 2020). Another significant difference is that girls are more self, parent, and teacher-motivated while boys are best motivated by their peers, especially of the same sex (Wilson, 2015).

This implies that boys may most likely have a different learning support strategy and reflection learning strategy than girls. Girls enjoy learning different strategies, whereas boys need more structure and routines, especially in learning new and complex content. This may be because boys' need for active participation has been attributed to how their brains process the information.

Table 5 Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Emotional Response Strategies

Emotional Response Strategies	Mean	SD	VI
1. I find it important to complete my flexible online learning experience. <i>(Nakikita ko ang kahalagahan na matapos ko ang aking karanasan sa "flexible online learning".)</i>	3.8182	1.07794	Great Extent
2. It is important that I do my flexible online learning successfully. <i>(Mahalagang magawa ko ang aking "flexible online learning" ng matagumpay.)</i>	4.2045	.84635	Very Great Extent
3. Striving to learn in this flexible online learning is worth the effort. <i>(Ang pagsusumikap upang matuto sa "flexible online learning" ay makabuluhan.)</i>	3.7841	1.12902	Great Extent
4. I encourage myself to study to be rewarded. <i>(Hinihikayat ang aking sarili na mag-aral upang magkaroon ng gantimpala.)</i>	3.9773	.98234	Great Extent
5. I encourage myself with great things when I have completed what I have set for myself. <i>(Hinihimok ko ang aking sarili sa magagandang bagay kapag nakumpleto ko na ang naitakda ko para sa aking sarili.)</i>	3.7955	1.01889	Great Extent
6. I feel the importance of learning through flexible online learning. <i>(Nararamdaman ko ang kahalagahan ng natutuhan sa pamamagitan ng pag-aangkop ng online na pagkatuto.)</i>	3.7500	1.04221	Great Extent
7. Happy thoughts are helping me to concentrate on my studies. <i>(Ang mga masasayang saloobin ay nakakatulong sa akin na pagtuonang pansin ang aking pag-aaral.)</i>	4.2500	.91287	Very Great Extent
Mean	3.9399	.63694	Great Extent

Indicator two of table five on the importance of successfully doing flexible online learning and indicator seven on the assistance of happy thoughts to help concentrate on studies were rated to a very great extent, while the remaining indicators resulted to a great extent. These positively influenced the learners' emotional response strategy.

Findings show that in the extent of utilization of adaptive learning in emotional response strategies, pupils in this new mode of learning possess a positive attitude. Flexibility during online learning has a great value bearing the highest contributing factor in their successful journey in learning.

Table 5.1 Differences in the Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Emotional Response Strategy when grouped According to Selected Variables

Profile Variables	Mean	SD	Df	F	P	VI
Age						
8-10 years old	3.9683	.63868	1	.274	.602	Not Significant
11-13 years old	3.8950	.64111				
Sex						
Male	3.8286	.64653	1	2.876	.094	Not Significant
Female	4.0565	.61258				
Grade Level						
grade 3	4.1429	.66207	3	3.429	.021	Significant
grade 4	3.6746	.59167				
grade 5	4.1086	.59659				
grade 6	3.7347	.58604				
Education of Father						
high school	3.5397	.79468	3	2.841	.043	Significant
college level	4.0255	.48881				
college graduate	3.9196	.65691				
postgraduate	4.6667	.35952				
Education of Mother						
high school	3.8254	.60516	3	1.052	.374	Not Significant
college level	4.1654	.56195				
college graduate	3.8903	.63304				
postgraduate	3.8214	1.05865				
Occupation of Father						
unemployed	3.8182	.59759	1	5.645	.020	Significant
laborer	4.1429	.65757				
Occupation of Mother						
housewife	3.8095	.62702	2	1.052	.354	Not Significant
laborer	4.0025	.64143				
caste occupation	4.2857	.				
Size of Family						
1-4 members	3.9221	.53220	1	.023	.880	Not Significant
above 4 members	3.9459	.67182				
Number of Siblings						
no sibling	3.7241	.63880	2	2.580	.082	Not Significant
with 1-3 siblings	4.0714	.58654				
with above 3 siblings	4.0420	.62355				

Table 5.1 revealed the students' differences in emotional response strategies occurred between Grade Levels: Grade 3, Grade 4, Grade 5, and Grade 6. It also revealed differences in the father's educational background, with high school obtaining the lowest mean and all other educational levels, as well as the father's occupation.

Emotional experiences are natural, important and crucial in the context of education, as emotions fix the learners understanding of the lessons. Exercises, tests, and homework are associated with emotional factors that include irritability, anxiety, and fatigue. Even the subjects discussed in the study affect emotions that involve the

ability to read and remember. The use of online educational forums, which are slowly changing the traditional face-to-face learning environment, is growing. This may evoke different emotions in students. In this study's case, a stay-at-home parent is a father, and should carefully consider emotion in education to enhance students' engagement and enrich their long-term concentration and knowledge (Tyng, et al., 2017).

This implies that availability in time positively contributes to their children's emotional development. Significantly, in their emotional adjustments in this situation, their father became one of their support system and guidance. A child's sense of self-worth and aptitude, their comprehension of the world around them, their views about where they fit into the scheme of things, how significant adults in their life treat each other, how decisions are made, and how youngsters feel, and how problems are solved significantly impacts their emotional well-being.

Table 6 Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Helpline Strategies

Helpline Strategies	Mean	SD	VI
1. When I do not fully understand something, I ask my parent/s or sibling for ideas in this flexible online learning. <i>(Kapag hindi ko lubos na naintindihan ang isang bagay, hinihiling ko sa aking magulang / kapatid o mga kapatid ang mga ideya sa kakayahang umangkop sa online na pag-aaral.)</i>	4.1818	.96544	Great Extent
2. I share my problem with my parents so they know what I am struggling with and how to solve my problems. <i>(Binabahagi ko ang aking problema sa aking mga magulang para malaman nila ang aking pagpupunyagi at kung paano ito mabigyang solusyon.)</i>	4.1023	.91022	Great Extent
3. I share my problem with my siblings so they know what I am struggling with and how to solve my problems. <i>(Binabahagi ko ang aking problema sa aking mga kapatid para malaman nila ang aking pagpupunyagi at kung paano ito mabigyang solusyon.)</i>	2.1705	1.53295	Minimal Extent
4. I am persistent in getting help from my parents in this flexible online learning. <i>(Pursigido akong makakakuha ng tulong mula sa aking mga magulang sa pag-aangkop ng online na pagkatuto.)</i>	3.7386	1.07740	Great Extent
5. I ask help from my parents for they are capable of tutoring me during remote learning sessions. <i>(Humihingi ako ng tulong mula sa aking mga magulang dahil sila ay may kakayahang turuan ako sa mga malayuang sesyon ng pagkatuto.)</i>	3.9545	1.06035	Great Extent
6. I ask help from my siblings for they are capable of tutoring me during remote learning sessions. <i>(Humihingi ako ng tulong mula sa aking mga kapatid dahil sila ay may kakayahang turuan ako sa mga malayuang sesyon ng pagkatuto.)</i>	2.1136	1.41772	Minimal Extent
7. When I do not fully understand something, I ask my parent/s or sibling for ideas in this flexible online learning. <i>(Kapag hindi ko lubos na naintindihan ang isang bagay, hinihiling ko sa aking magulang / kapatid o mga kapatid ang mga ideya sa kakayahang umangkop sa online na pag-aaral.)</i>	3.3769	.76585	Moderate
Mean	4.1818	.96544	Great Extent

For Table 6, adaptive learning helpline strategies indicators 1, 2, 4, and 5 showed a result of great extent on the face-to-face interaction at home while helpline strategies indicators 3 and 6 show the minimal extent, and helpline strategies indicator 7 shows a "moderate" result. Supporting a learner in this new learning mode must be considered an integral part of children's learning - having adequate time to carry out the learning process. At the same time, this

communication must be recognized as a critical part of parenting, and parents must commit to meeting their children's emotional and developmental stages.

Table 6.1 Differences in the Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning in Helpline Strategy when grouped According to Selected Variables

Profile Variables	Mean	SD	Df	F	P	VI
<i>Age</i>						
8-10 years old	3.4198	.68813	1	.435	.511	Not Significant
11-13 years old	3.3088	.88204				
<i>Sex</i>						
male	3.3593	.75958	1	.048	.827	Significant
female	3.3953	.78091				
<i>Grade Level</i>						
grade 3	3.6181	.62454	3	1.492	.223	Not Significant
grade 4	3.2778	.68361				
grade 5	3.1800	.84973				
grade 6	3.4206	.84265				
<i>Education of Father</i>						
high school	3.1296	.79398	3	.932	.429	Significant
college level	3.3036	.72443				
college graduate	3.4340	.78229				
postgraduate	3.8889	.83887				
<i>Education of Mother</i>						
high school	2.8889	.60093	3	1.976	.124	Not Significant
college level	3.4912	.73172				
college graduate	3.4464	.77922				
postgraduate	2.9583	.76225				
<i>Occupation of Father</i>						
unemployed	3.0848	.63007	1	27.930	.000	Significant
laborer	3.8636	.73060				
<i>Occupation of Mother</i>						
Housewife	3.0000	.60490	2	7.536	.001	Significant
laborer	3.5526	.76451				
caste occupation	4.6667	.00000				
<i>Size of Family</i>						
1-4 members	3.2727	.82383	1	.540	.465	Not Significant
above 4 members	3.4116	.74891				
<i>Number of Siblings</i>						
no sibling	3.0920	.49519	2	4.399	.015	Significant
with 1-3 siblings	3.1458	.79401				
with above 3 siblings	3.5752	.83620				

As shown in table 6.1, there are significant differences between males' and females' utilization of adaptive learning in helpline strategies. Significant differences are also seen in the father's educational background, father's occupation, occupation of mother, and the number of siblings.

It shows a correlation between children's understanding and strategies with all the support systems in his/her environment that act as a helpline. This result reveals that adults should invest in child development. Each has its own ways and practices of nurturing or developing a child, and when information is shared, each student is more likely to succeed. This explains that all the children's experiences, both inside and outside the school, help to cultivate the feeling that someone cares.

One study shows that learning online seems to be a new concept compared with conventional schooling or face-to-face class, and the chances of things not working out are far from over in the minds of parents. Using modern technology, parents need to keep an eye on their children at all times and at the same time provide the ideal environment for them to gain the required skills.

Realizing that it is not a shame to ask for help if a student feels tired: maybe a simple adjustment, or may require a long-term change, but the cost of doing nothing over time will damage one's physical and emotional health. Educators, parents, and children do daily adapt to the ever-changing world of technology, and recently, many of the tried-and-true professional learning experiences have transformed us. Since teaching is no longer done in school solely by the teacher instead, teaching is happening at home either remote or virtual where parents are also working as teachers, parents need to keep abreast with the demands of this learning environment by allocating ample time acting as parent-teacher, study and learn the lessons with the children, and assigning significant others of the siblings or family member as tutor.

Table 7 Differences in the Extent of Utilization of Adaptive Learning when taken as a whole and when grouped According to Selected Variables

Profile Variables	Mean	SD	Df	F	P	VI
<i>Age</i>						
8-10 years old	3.7443	.57843	1	.323	.571	Not Significant
11-13 years old	3.6693	.63937				
<i>Sex</i>						
Male	3.5734	.61040	1	5.406	.022	Significant
Female	3.8638	.55833				
<i>Grade Level</i>						
grade 3	3.8272	.60123	3	1.347	.265	Not Significant
grade 4	3.5698	.58247				
grade 5	3.8314	.60573				
grade 6	3.5739	.59222				
<i>Education of Father</i>						
high school	3.1656	.54624	3	4.186	.008	Significant
college level	3.8026	.47290				
college graduate	3.7291	.62936				
postgraduate	4.3302	.33351				
<i>Education of Mother</i>						
high school	3.4730	.62694	3	.709	.549	Not Significant
college level	3.8125	.56823				
college graduate	3.7296	.60243				
postgraduate	3.5988	.74159				
<i>Occupation of Father</i>						
unemployed	3.5754	.58539	1	8.672	.004	Significant
laborer	3.9485	.55804				
<i>Occupation of Mother</i>						
housewife	3.5343	.60673	2	2.314	.105	Not Significant
laborer	3.8028	.58319				
caste occupation	4.1619	.				
<i>Size of Family</i>						
1-4 members	3.6961	.59949	1	.030	.864	Not Significant
above 4 members	3.7217	.60488				
<i>Number of Siblings</i>						

no sibling	3.5366	.57524	2	2.067	.133	Not Significant
with 1-3 siblings	3.7149	.68627				
with above 3 siblings	3.8170	.58864				

Table 7 on the differences in the extent of utilization of adaptive learning when grouped according to selected variables revealed that there is a difference between males and females and the father's educational background. This implies that females, as a whole, have better utilization of the adaptive learning strategies than males while parents, especially the father, considering the educational background, occupation, and the available time the farther spends with the child's learning sessions, play a significant role in establishing a connection and guide to their children and as the home facilitator in this flexible online mode of learning. Furthermore, most of the students cannot answer all their modules independently; that is why they need the assistance of others. The family members of the learners play a vital role in education today. Lastly, parents must provide their children with a productive learning environment to help them focus more on their flexible online learning.

The article termed Gender Issues in Primary Education Research-Based Strategies to Meet Different Learning Needs for Boys and Girls by Bonomo (2010) explains that sex is relevant to cognition in elementary pupils. Female students do better in the speaking and writing fields because the left side of the brain that controls these functions grows earlier in girls than boys.

Furthermore, according to Ceka & Murati (2016) article entitled In Praise of the Fathers: Ways Based on the Survey of the Effects of Fathers Improved Children, children without fathers or their father's guidance tend to have emotional and moral problems or are two times more likely to drop out of school. However, those who have their father's attention, encouragement, and guidance develop greater confidence. Mothers are a stable place for children, but fathers allow their children to branch out independently. They encourage their children to explore the world. As the saying goes, "The mother sets the roots for her child, and the father prepares the wings for the child."

Table 8 Correlations of Adaptive Learning Strategies and Pupils' Performance

Learning Strategies	N	R	P	VI
Planning strategy	88	.437**	.000	Significant
Doing Strategy	88	.405**	.000	Significant
Reflection Strategy	88	.376**	.000	Significant
Emotional Response Strategy	88	.430**	.000	Significant
Helpline Strategy	88	.311**	.003	Significant
When taken as a whole	88	.480**	.000	Significant

Table 8, on the correlation of adaptive learning strategies and pupils' academic performance, shows a significant result in all strategies, namely the planning strategy, the doing strategy, the reflection strategy, the emotional-response strategy, and the helpline strategy. In correlating adaptive learning strategies and pupils' academic performance, the final grade of the participants of the study as their academic performance is used upon approval of the School Principal.

Indeed, many studies are showing that teacher presence is associated with student success or failure in learning, at least in online learning. When students perceive that the teacher was not in a face-to-face position, both student performance and completion rates dropped. This is relatable to flexible online learning, where face-to-face interaction with a teacher is limited. Good and timely, emotional, academic and parent-teacher support for students (parents or siblings) distinguishes between the successes and failures of such students.

According to a study done by Dr. Mollie Galloway of Lewis and Clark College, kids who spend more time doing homework are more behaviourally engaged in school. and have developed some learning strategies, they also

become more worried because of too much work that causes stress, and the effectiveness of learning diminishes. Just because there are a lot of home activities or work a learner does, does not mean the learner learns. Any work assigned to students should be designed to cultivate learning and development (Galloway, 2018).

This implies that one of the benefits of flexible online teaching is the acquisition of better reading skills among students. By engaging in learning the concepts presented in the lesson, learners feel a sense of commitment to the tasks assigned to them. With a lot of help, and little or no help from family members, students develop on their own. They learn how to read; they are empowered, leading towards better academic performance, improved school activities participation and increased self-esteem and confidence. This may however very evident in schools with strict admission policies and catering to only a limited number of select students.

In this new norm of education, students should follow some subjects or activities appropriately to avoid congestion or delivery delays, which may interfere with their academic performance.

Conclusions

The study was conducted to find out the adaptive learning strategies of the pupils of one private elementary school in Murcia. Based on the results and findings it showed that; Most of the respondents' parents were on college-level/degrees. It also revealed that most of the participants' mothers work, leaving their children under their husbands' care and supervision. Female students use their learning strategy plan better than men in this emerging educational trend of curriculum and instructional delivery. Older students also used their flexible learning strategies better than younger students. Age factor, parents' educational background, and parents' occupation did not significantly impact the respondents' adaptive learning strategies. The respondents' adaptive learning strategies and academic achievement have a significant relationship with each other.

Implications

While most mothers leave their children under the care and supervision of their husbands, the mother can still guide the growth of the student by working in partnership with the father as a child's support system. Parental involvement in their child's life improves a student's academic performance and prepares them for better lives. Brigada Eswela programs and initiatives require a robust implementation policy putting more premiums to parents-school-engaging activities to develop confidence and strong-esteem to learners. Undertaking diverse instructional delivery systems is the new trend that schools should continually adapt and improve not just in accordance to the needs of the learners but also to the needs of the time and the call of glocalization.

Recommendations

Parents and teachers may encourage male students to put more effort into their academic study not just for grades but for their overall progress. Furthermore, teachers may regularly communicate with the learners and their parents to monitor each pupil's academic progress. Due to the unavailability of face-to-face classes, parents are encouraged to provide guidance and supervision to their children. Especially during the new learning modalities, they should empower them to engage and lead their children with values as the first educators. Parents-school-community engagement may be strengthened through creation of parent-school-community-friendly environment that allows open-door policy planning, formulation and implementation of curricular and extra-curricular related activities promoting learners' holistic development.

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